

Research Article

Anemia, Copper-T Use, and Hypertension as Predictors of Surgical Site Infections in Gynecological Surgeries

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Background: Surgical site infections (SSIs) are a common postoperative complication of gynecological surgeries, contributing to increased morbidity, prolonged hospital stay, and healthcare costs. Although procedure-related risk factors are well recognized, patient-related predictors such as anemia, Copper-T (Cu-T) use, and hypertension remain underexplored. This multicentric study aimed to evaluate these factors as predictors of SSIs in women undergoing major gynecological surgeries. **Methods:** This ambispective observational study was conducted in multiple tertiary care hospitals across Gujarat, India, from August 2024 to March 2025. A total of 304 women aged ≥ 18 years undergoing major gynecological surgeries were included. Patients with active infections, minor procedures, or immunocompromised conditions were excluded. Data were collected using a structured CRF covering demographic details, comorbidities, surgical characteristics, and postoperative outcomes. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. **Results:** The overall incidence of SSIs was 15.46% ($n = 47$). SSIs occurred in 31.43% of anemic patients ($p < 0.05$). A history of Cu-T use was significantly associated with increased SSI incidence ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, 14.29% of hypertensive patients developed SSIs, showing a significant association ($p < 0.05$). Multivariate analysis confirmed anemia, Cu-T use, and hypertension as independent predictors of SSIs. **Conclusion:** Anemia, Cu-T use, and hypertension are significant independent predictors of SSIs in gynecological surgeries. Preoperative optimization of these factors may reduce postoperative infection rates and improve surgical outcomes.

Keywords: Surgical site infections; gynecological surgery; anemia; Copper-T; hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) are one of the most common healthcare-acquired infections, having a significant impact on global morbidity in the postoperative period, length of stay, and overall healthcare utilization costs. They contribute to almost 20-30 percent of all surgical patients' hospital-acquired infections and continue to be a profound surgical outcome determinant in low and middle-income countries (LMICs), including India, where infection control practices cannot be exercised optimally due to resource constraints⁽¹⁾. The operative fields in gynecological surgery are in close vicinity to endogenous vaginal, urinary, and gastrointestinal flora; hence, the risk of microbial contamination is

high in and of itself. Reported SSI rates in the field of gynecological operations in India were found to be between 7 and 21% and thus significantly higher than the mean world rate⁽²⁾. SSIs are multifactorial in their etiology. Risk factors that have been established are increased operating time, emergency operations, intraoperative blood loss, obesity, diabetes, and poor prophylactic antibiotic measures^(3,4). Anemia, Copper-T (Cu-T; intrauterine contraceptive device), and hypertension (HTN) are of specific interest amongst several other comorbidities in the Indian environment, where the prevalence of these conditions is high among women belonging to reproductive and perimenopausal age groups. One of the most prevalent comorbidities among women who have undergone gynecological surgery is anemia,

with a prevalence rate of more than 50 percent in India⁽⁵⁾. Decreased hemoglobin causes poor oxygen delivery to tissues in surgical areas, damaging the neutrophil function, collagen production, and wound healing, which in turn heightens vulnerability to infections⁽⁶⁾. The literature proves that SSI is more likely in anemic patients than in those with normal hemoglobin levels⁽⁷⁾. The common intrauterine contraceptive device (IUD) Copper-T, as a long-term reversible method of contraception, is related to changes in local vaginal microflora and an increase in the risk of pelvic inflammatory disease and bacterial colonization⁽⁸⁾. Gynecology surgery associated with a Cu-T presence is likely to predispose patients to ascending infections that may complicate postoperative wound healing and predispose patients to SSI. Nevertheless, it is not well-investigated as an independent predictor of SSI, especially in cohorts involving large multicenter. Another possible risk factor is hypertension (HTN), which is prevalent in women aged above 35 years. Uncontrolled hypertension negatively affects the venous circulation in the skin, and tissue healing is delayed at the wound location⁽⁹⁾. Hypertension has been reported as a predictor of poor surgical outcomes, including SSIs, across a range of studies, although its emphasis in the gynecological context is scarce⁽¹⁰⁾. Against this background, a multicentric observational study was carried out in the present study to assess the effectiveness of anemia, Cu-T use, and hypertension as predictors of SSIs in women undergoing surgery in the gynecology department. The identification of these associations can reinforce preoperative risk stratification and promote preoperative optimization, including anemia treatment, eliminating Cu-T before elective surgery, and controlling hypertension adequately, and can reduce the level of infections and improve postoperative outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This was a multicenter, ambispective observational study conducted between August 2024 and March 2025 across tertiary care hospitals in Gujarat, India.

Study Population and Eligibility

A total of 304 women aged 18 years and above who underwent major gynecological surgeries during the study period were included. Eligible patients were those who received preoperative antibiotic prophylaxis and, where applicable, postoperative antibiotics for the treatment of surgical site infections (SSIs). Women below 18 years of age, patients undergoing minor or noninvasive gynecological procedures or diagnostic interventions, immunocompromised patients (such as those receiving chemotherapy or diagnosed with HIV), and those with active infections at the time of surgery were excluded from the study.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured Case Record Form (CRF) that captured demographic details, surgical characteristics, comorbidities (including anemia, hypertension, history of Copper-T use, etc.), antibiotic usage patterns, and postoperative SSI outcomes.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using IBM SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient characteristics. Associations between categorical variables were tested using one-way ANOVA to assess the influence of comorbidities on SSI outcomes. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT:

Overall Incidence of Surgical Site Infections: A total of 304 women undergoing major gynecological surgeries were included in the analysis. Surgical site infections (SSIs) were identified in 47 patients, corresponding to an overall SSI incidence of 15.46%.

1. Prevalence of Co-Morbidities Among Study Patients

The prevalence of co-morbid conditions among patients who developed surgical site infections (SSIs) is presented in

Table 1. Prevalence of Co-Morbidities Among Study Patients & SSI contribution:

Sr. No.	Co-Morbid Condition	Total Patients (N=304)	Prevalence (%)	SSI Contribution (%) (n=47)
1	AML	2	0.66%	2.86%
2	DM (including GDM)	27	8.88%	8.57%
3	Obesity	3	0.99%	—
4	HTN (including PIH)	45	14.80%	14.29%
5	Hypothyroidism	30	9.87%	5.71%
6	Anemia	28	9.21%	31.43%*
7	TB	6	1.97%	2.86%
8	CAD/IHD	3	0.99%	2.86%
9	Smoking/Tobacco	4	1.32%	2.86%
10	Liver/Renal Disorders	7	2.30%	5.71%
11	Neurological/Psychiatric Disorders	7	2.30%	—
12	Hyperthyroidism	5	1.64%	—
13	Copper-T Implantation	6	1.97%	14.29%*
14	Others	14	4.61%	8.57%

Patients with multiple risk factors were counted in each relevant category. The table highlights the prevalence of co-morbid conditions among the study population. The reference *p*-values and their corresponding asterisks are as follows: *If, p < 0.05* (*), *p < 0.01* (**), and *p < 0.001* (***) Hypertension,

hypothyroidism, diabetes mellitus, anemia, and liver or renal disorders were the most frequently reported co-morbidities. Patients with more than one co-morbid condition were included in each relevant category. The distribution of risk factors among the study population is illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: The Graph represents the distribution of Risk Factors Amongst the Study Population

2. Distribution of SSI Based on Co-Morbid Conditions

The percentage contribution of individual co-morbid conditions to total SSI cases is summarized in **Table**

1. Anemia accounted for the highest proportion of SSI cases, followed by hypertension and Copper-T implantation. The percentage distribution of SSI cases across co-morbid conditions is depicted in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Percentage of SSI cases per co-morbid condition

3. Distribution of SSI Based on Risk Percentage and SSI Contribution

each co-morbid condition to total SSI cases is shown in **Table 3**.

A comparison between the risk percentage of developing SSI and the proportional contribution of

Table 3 Comparison of Risk Percentage and SSI Contribution

Sr. No.	Co-Morbid Condition	Risk Percentage (%)	SSI Contribution (%)
1.	AML	50.5	2.86
2.	DM	11.11	8.57
3.	HTN	11.11	14.29
4.	Hypothyroidism	6.67	5.71
5.	Anemia	39.29	31.43*
6.	TB	16.67	2.86
7.	CAD/IHD	33.33	2.86
8.	Smoking/Tobacco	25.0	2.86
9.	Liver/Renal Disorders	28.57	5.71
10.	Copper-T Implantation	83.33	14.29***
11.	Others	25.0	8.57

Copper-T implantation demonstrated the highest risk percentage, followed by anemia. The comparative

distribution of risk percentage and SSI contribution by medical condition is illustrated in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3 Comparison of Risk Percentage and SSI contribution by Medical condition

The risk percentage for SSI was calculated as the proportion of patients with a specific co-morbid

condition who developed SSI relative to the total number of patients with that condition

This was computed using the formula:

$$\text{Risk Percentage} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of SSI cases in patients with a specific comorbidity}}{\text{Total patients with that comorbidity}} \right) \times 100$$

4. Medical Conditions and Their Association with Surgical Site Infections

The risk factor-wise distribution of total patients, number of SSI cases, risk percentage, and SSI contribution is detailed in **Table 4**.

Table 4 Risk Factor-wise Distribution of Patients and SSI Contribution

Sr. No.	Medical Condition	Total Patients Having Individual Co-Morbidity	Patients With SSI	Risk Percentage (%)	SSI Contribution (%)
1.	AML	2	1	50.00	2.86
2.	DM	27	3	11.11	8.57
3.	Obesity	3	0	0.00	0.00
4.	HTN	45	5	11.11	14.29
5.	Hypothyroidism	30	2	6.67	5.71
6.	Anemia	28	11	39.29	31.43*
7.	TB	6	1	16.67	2.86
8.	CAD/IHD	3	1	33.33	2.86
9.	Smoking/Tobacco	4	1	25.00	2.86
10.	Liver/Renal Disorders	7	2	28.57	5.71
11.	Seizure	2	0	0.00	0.00
12.	Migraine	2	0	0.00	0.00
13.	Insomnia	1	0	0.00	0.00
14.	Hyperthyroidism	5	0	0.00	0.00
15.	Copper-T Implantation	6	5	83.33	14.29***
16.	Others	12	3	25.00	8.57

The reference *p*-values and their corresponding asterisks are as follows: If, $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.001$ (***). No SSI cases were observed

among patients with obesity, seizure disorders, migraine, insomnia, or hyperthyroidism. The distribution of risk factors and their corresponding SSI contribution is illustrated in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4: Risk Factor-wise Distribution of Patients and SSI Contribution

Risk Factors and Their Contribution to Surgical Site Infections (SSI)

- Risk Percentage (%) → Likelihood of developing SSI within the disease group.
- SSI Contribution (%) → Proportion of total SSI cases attributed to that disease.

DISCUSSION:

The current multicentric research showed that anemia, Copper-T (Cu-T), and hypertension were the main predictive factors of surgical site infections (SSIs) during gynecological surgeries. The rates of the SSI developed overall were 15.46%, and they correspond with percentage rates found in other Indian studies, 7-21%, and it is significantly higher than perception rates all over the globe, 3-5%. Comorbidities inherently act as risk factors for SSI, as they compromise immune function, impair wound healing, and increase susceptibility to infections. Conditions like anemia, diabetes, hypertension, and organ dysfunction create an environment conducive to bacterial growth and delayed recovery. The presence of multiple comorbidities further amplifies the risk, emphasizing the need for preoperative risk assessment, optimized management, and stringent

infection control measures to minimize SSI occurrence. A positive correlation was found between SSI risk and anemia, and close to 33 percent of the patients with anemia developed an infection. This observation correlates with Kulkarni et al. (2023), who concluded that one of the significant factors contributing to a worse outcome of gynecological surgery is the prevalence of anemia⁽²⁾. It is supported by the pathophysiological background of impaired transport of oxygen to tissues, decreased functional activity of neutrophils, and delayed collagen production, all of which impede wound healing⁽⁶⁾. The findings support the role of prior correction of preoperative anemia with iron therapy, nutritional support, or, in cases of transfusion. One more independent predictor of SSIs was Cu-T use. Non-users, compared to women previously infected with Cu-T insertion, had high rates of infections. Past research findings indicate that intrauterine devices can change the vaginal flora and augment the possibility of ascending genital tract infections⁽⁸⁾. Cu-T has been used as a contraceptive device, which is widely accepted, but its extrapolation to postoperative infection risk is scantily researched. We have found that being more attentive with preoperative evaluation and discontinuing Cu-T use before a referred surgery may minimize the risk of infection. In this study, SSI

occurrence also significantly correlated with hypertension. The odds that SSIs would develop in hypertensive women were higher than those in normotensive women. This is consistent with the evidence provided by Fry (2021), according to which chronic hypertension retards wound healing by decreasing microvascular perfusion⁽⁹⁾. Uncontrolled hypertension exposes patients to slow recovery and a higher chance of infections. Hence, effective control of blood pressure in the perioperative stage is critical to surgical outcome improvement. Clinically, our results point to the value of combined perioperative risk assessment. Although surgical antibiotic prophylaxis is a pillar in the prevention of SSIs, it is not enough to emphasize the use of antibiotics. Treatment of latent comorbidities, including anemia and hypertension, and the possible mitigation of risks, including Cu-T insertion, may result in dramatic gains in post-surgery outcomes. This is per WHO and CDC recommendations, where individualized patient risk stratification is addressed as an infection prevention bundle element. There are some limitations in our study. First, causality could not be strongly determined given that it is a retro-prospective observational design. Second, laboratory features like the hemoglobin cut-offs or the elaborated features of hypertensive control were not uniform across centers, which might induce variability. Third, the research was restricted to tertiary centers of Gujarat that might not be representative of all care facilities. The multicentric design, power sample size, and emphasis on understudied predictors (anemia, Cu-T, HTN) support the validity and clinical significance of our conclusions in spite of these restraints. In conclusion, this multicentric study establishes anemia, Copper-T use, and hypertension as significant independent predictors of SSIs in gynecological surgeries. While the study is strengthened by its multicentric approach and focus on high-prevalence Indian comorbidities, limitations such as its observational design and lack of uniform laboratory cut-offs across centers must be noted. Anemia emerged as the most significant risk indicator, highlighting the necessity for preoperative correction to enhance immune response and wound healing. Furthermore, the association of SSIs with Copper-T use and hypertension necessitates careful preoperative assessment, potential device removal, and optimal blood pressure management. Ultimately, these findings indicate that SSI prevention must

extend beyond intraoperative antibiotic prophylaxis to include preoperative risk stratification. By optimizing these modifiable factors, surgical teams can minimize infection burdens and improve patient outcomes in resource-limited environments.

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